

Riedel Thermo-ventilar-solar- cell-generator without photoelectric effect (TVSCG)

Introduction

Thermo-ventilar-solar- cell-generator without photoelectric effect but water current usage. A water pressure and divergent temperature gradient closed cycle based solar energy dependent cell. The two special cells are heated by huge accumulation lenses that channel the accumulated sunlight on the two special cells that are held red (to symbolize heat). Those two warm up and heat creates pressure. The cells with the one way ventils are not fully filled with water. Just enough (adjustable water level). The generator uses distilled water to circumvent calcification of the one way valves. The pressure builds up and increases the volume above the water comun, wich pushes the water with pressure through the one way valves (wich are at bottom level). Wich also drives the propellers. The propellers drive the rods (wich could be fastened to magnetic elements so there is no leakage point, but per now this is not drawn in the drawings). The rods transmit kinetic energy (that is added to the entire system in form of heat from the sunlight) to the rolls, the rolls transmit it to the belt, the belt to a bigger roll that transmits the kinetic energy into rotation of the cobber coil inside the electricity generator, this works totally without silicon and without the Einstein photoelectric effect.

Since the system is closed it has a finite volume capacity that is determined by the overall architecture and material strength. Therefore the TVSCG has an emergency valve, such that the apparatus does not explodes. (water vapor is a greenhouse gas as green as it seems, therefore one has to has a cooling tub attached to it, to reduce the climate footprint). The drawings show 7 x 2 cells, but the TVSCG apparatus can be scaled arbitrarily, for example to 20-40 cells. The TVSCG shows that we are not purely limited by electric current, or wind or solar, we can create new kinds of green-generators. We can create other currents with finite cells or subunits and valves. This makes us independent from silica, and manufacturing. Also the TVSCG appartus is thought to be so cheap that it would be easy to replace it instead of paying maintenance costs.

Cells in metal case

1 x metal case that contains the water filled cell

Emergency valvex 1x per machine

Cells in metal case (heat gradient cycle)

1 x water filled cell with one way valves that form aclosed cycle Where water flows from high temperature → lower temperature

See trough view of cells in metal case

Intermidiate view 1

Print friendly side view

Intermediate view 1

Intermediate view 2

Outside view (with open side)

Outside view (with tripod accumulation lenses and all sides closed and painted (against corrosion))

